

TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE

Biodiversity, Seed Varieties and Seed System BIHAR

Seed Conservation Structure found in Jharkhand: This structure found in only one home during survey.

Munirka Devi, Bahronki,
Jharkhand

Uses for seed storage

Uses for curd

Fig.- "Mitti ki Kothiya" – A Traditional Seed Conservation Structure
(Image taken by Mr. Vikas Arora during field survey in Feb 2020)

To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT

BY
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Under the project
Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

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ABBREVIATIONS

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PAIRVI - Public Advocacy Initiatives For Rights and Values In India

Botanical Name of Crops:

Arhar - *Cajanuscajan*

Kulthi- *Macrotyloma uniflorum*

Mustard - *Brassica nigra*

Urad - *Vigna mungo*

Til - *Sesamum indicum*

Moong - *Vigna radiata*

Khesari - *Lathyrussativus*

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We acknowledge with thanks for the participation of many individuals, farmers officials of KrishiVigyan Kendra for completing the survey and collecting the data from the farmers' community.

This survey was conducted by the the state coordinator and project coordinator with the help of IRDC community level approach.

The survey consisted of Field level data collection by state coordinator Mr. Upender Kumar and Mr. Subhash Dubey assistance at local level under monitoring of project coordinator Mr. Vikas Arora at PAIRVI (Public Advocacy Initiatives For Rights and Values In India).

The team completed the survey in February 2020, but the survey form could not be parceled to PAIRVI office, Delhi due to COVID-19 lockdown. Lockdown started on 22nd March (Janta-curfew by Honorable Prime Minister of India) 2020.However, it has been submitted in August 2020.

INTRODUCTION

The BSF IVth Cycle project in India “Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population” is an FAO fund project funded under ITPGR.

The aim of the project is to enhance the availability and on-farm conservation of resilient varieties of pulses (traditional varieties, varieties procured from gene banks as well as under-utilized species of pulses) and oil seeds for cultivation during the rice fallowseason.

The two main objectives of the survey are:

1. House hold surveys to document indigenous knowledge on local varieties and local seedsystem
2. To establish women centric indicators for base line surveys & evaluations and develop strategies to ensure their inclusion in theproject.

Other objectives:

1. To understand the Needs and Vulnerability for the crops specially for pulses andoilseed
2. To know about the crops grown in the area and historical change in biodiversity and how can one revives the pulses and oilseedbiodiversity.

PROJECT AREA

5.1 Location:

Block- Chakai, District-Jamui, Bihar

CHAKAI BLOCK

Fig.: Project location at goggle map

5.2 Selected Villages:

1. CHEHARA
2. GHATIYANI
3. BAREDIH
4. BADLADIH
5. PARSATAND
6. SIRSI

5.3 Farmers with GPS location:

See Annexure -I

5.4 Occupation and Income:

Agriculture and livestock along daily wage labor is the main source of income in the selected five villages of Chakai block. Both Kharif and Rabi crops are grown and the major agricultural produce consists of monsoon rice and potato. The agricultural system is not mechanized and most of the farmers are using their traditional knowledge. The new generation, youth groups are not considering agriculture as an occupation. The aged farmers are facing more vulnerability as well as future food security is in question mark. Due to being a mountainous area, the land here is rocky. The pebbles and stone parts are found more in the soils here. Due to being a step-like farm, there is no stagnation of water in the fields. Due to lack of other facilities for irrigation of fields, farmers have to depend on monsoon rains. Paddy cultivation is the main crop of this region, but it is hardly possible to cultivate it once in a year. Almost all the land remains vacant after paddy cultivation. The average annual income of farmers is Rs. 45000.00 which is very tough to maintain their families resulted in they are not focusing on agriculture and shifting to other occupation.

METHODOLOGY

Household survey (questionnaire survey) : Household survey was carried out in 7 villages covering a total of 50 households. Every household was covered through a questionnaire developed in Hindi. The questionnaire was structured into two parts. First part of questionnaire divided into five sections including a general section and the second part of questionnaire into one section for gathering the information about gender equality and women role in agriculture in the project areas.

Table - 1 Sections in Questionnaire

Section	Cover	Questions No.	Summary
Part –I			
Farmer General Info	Land holding. Irrigation facilities Sources of income	17	Most of the farmers are belonging to ST and SC community. They are poor and marginal and average landholding capacity is 1.2 acre. They are not having own irrigation facilities but recently irrigation department installed solar irrigations systems by using dug well and tube wells. The main source of income is agriculture and daily wage selling at agriculture and tea gardens fields. The seasonal migration is also another source of income.
Information about Farming	Crop grown Biodiversity 20-25 years ago Reason behind changes	3	20 to 25 years back farmers have grown paddy, jute, potato, onion, different kinds of pulses and vegetables. But right now they are mainly growing monsoon paddy, potato and some vegetables. Now they are not growing pulses at all since 1996-97. The reasons behind changing of crops and farmers choices are including the followings- Lack of irrigation and uneven rainfalls. Increasing the temperature resulted in soil moisture or water retention of soil is low as well as pH value is also not in favorable condition. Seeds are locally not available especially pulse seeds. Lack of market linkages and quick fluctuation of market price of farmers products. Farmers are having limited knowledge on diversified crops cultivation and modern technologies.
Info about pulses and Oilseed crops	Pulses and Oilseed biodiversity	9	Farmers used to cultivate different kinds of pulses and oil seeds including pigeon pea, chickpeas, black gram, horse gram, pea, lentils, green grams, sesame, kidney beans, ground nuts, mustard etc. in two decades back. Now farmers in 21 st century almost forgotten to grow such diversified pulses and oilseeds except lentil, black gram, green gram and mustard. These selected crops are cultivating by few selected farmers in the winter season mainly for their own consumption.
Info about seed and seed system	Seed Varieties, Seed Storage and Seed storage	11	There is almost no seed storage capacity or arrangement in the project location. Just few farmers are keeping their seeds in polythene in their house and protecting from wet and sunlight. Normally they are purchasing from retail shops as well as accessing from government.
Needs and Vulnerability : Farmer's' perception on climate change	Animals and other vulnerable factors	5	The followings are needs and vulnerable factors in the context of climate change- The duration of monsoon season is decreasing year by year and dry season is increasing resulted in irrigation cost is increasing and farmers are facing more vulnerability. Less water consuming crops like pulses and oil seeds to be

			<p>grown but open grazing (plenty of cows and goat in the project villages) is the major constraint to grow such pulses and oil seeds.</p> <p>Sometime wild animals like elephants are also damaging the crops.</p> <p>Uneven rainfall and sometime flash flood due to heavy rain in July damaged the crops.</p> <p>Pulse seeds are very much sensitive resulted in it is always not available in the local market.</p> <p>Storm / wind and thunderstorms also damaged the pulses and oilseeds.</p>
Part- II			
Gender equality	Role of women in agriculture	19	<p>In the project location women farmers are playing vital role in the sector of agriculture. Women farmers are involved in land preparation, seedbed preparation, sowing/planting, harvesting etc. The male farmers are helping in ploughing and pests management. Women farmers are overburden in managing their domestic work, cooking, farming, livestock etc.</p>

FINDINGS

Findings from the survey have been divided into 6 sections.

7.1 Land demographics: Irrigated, rainfed and barren land

Land demographics provide a snapshot of the total land under irrigation, rainfed and barren land. Average land holding in the study villages are calculated keeping in mind the total land holding and the number of households owning agricultural land.

The proportion of irrigated versus non irrigated land was explored. As table 2 suggests 97.5% land in project village is under rain fed area, which receive only monsoon rain. That is indicating rice fallow area due to non-irrigated facilities in this area. Only two seasonal ponds are water sources in the selected villages. But ponds are not used for irrigation purposes.

Table - 2 : % Irrigated, Rainfed and Barren land

Sl. No.	Villages name	No. Of Surveyed	Av. Irrigated Land	Source of Irrigation	Av. Rainfed agriculture land/Rice fallow	Av. Barren land	% people interested to grow pulses and oilseed
1	Cehara	10	65%	Well and Pond	31%	4%	70%
2	Ghatiyani	10	62%	Well and Pond	36%%	2%	74%
3	Baredih	10	73%	Well and Pond	22%	5%	35%
4	Badladih	10	55%	Well and Pond	42%	3%	48%
5	Parsatand	10	46%	Well and Pond	47%	7%	55%
6	Sirsia	10		Well and Pond			
7	Basahra						

7.2 Crop Grown: Monsoon and Post Monsoon Season

The various crops grown in the study villages were explored. These have been bifurcated on the basis of the season: Kharif and Rabi.

Kharif Crops: Monsoon Season

Major: The major Kharif crops grown in the study villages include : 1) Rice (sowing June-July)

Minor: Urad/ Black Gram and Mustard appear to be grown only by a small percentage of farmers in the month of August - September and harvest with rice. Surveyed grown rice in total lower land and upper land is being barren. kharif season, they do not grow any other crop in this season.

Fig : % of farmers growing kharif crops
Small percentage of farmers grown Oilseed / Pulses in upper land

*Uncultivated land situated at the height and it is slopy land. Rice grown in the lower land where rain water collected.

100 % of surveyed grown Rice in lower land

Rabi Crops: Post Monsoon season

Major: The major Rabi crops grown in the study villages include: 1) Rice (harvested in Oct.)

Minor: Chana appear to be grown only by small percentage of farmers in the month of November.

Surveyed grown 20-30 % vegetable it's all land in irrigated part only, other 70 % to 80% is rice fallow and they not growing any crops.

Fig : % of farmers growing Rabi crops
Small percentage of farmers grown Oilseed, Pulses and Rice in lower land

Farmers growing Rabi crops

Rice
 Pulses
 Vegetables
 Oil Seeds
 Un Cultivated Land

Small percentage of farmers grown Oilseed, Pulses in upper land

Rice
 Vegetables
 Oilseed
 Pulses
 Uncultivated

Zaid Crops:

“Summer Moong” locally known as “garma moong” appear to be grown only by a small percentage of farmer in the month of April.

7.2.1 Crop Cycle:

Tribal has specific knowledge system to know about the appropriate time to sow the crops. For an example – local community / tribal farmers are not sowing / planting paddy before local festival. Their make-belief system says it makes less pest attack and high yield. Agriculture in India is highly dependent on the monsoons and can thus be called a gamble. Mostly literature present the one month period to sowing the crop. Farmer decided himself which date will be preferred in the one month period for sowing the crops. Tribal farmer of remote areas do not know about Indian meteorological data. They are used their own knowledge system to sowing the crop.

Table - 3: Crop Cycle for Major and Minor Crops in Rabi and Kharif Season

Season	Sowing Time	Harvesting Time	Major Crop	Current Pulses and Oilseed	20-25 years back Pulses and oilseed	Cropping Pattern
	15 June - 15 July	15 October to 15 November	Paddy	Arhar, Mize, Moong	Black gram and green gram	Mono-cropping
Kharif	Mid August- mid September	Mid November- mid December	-	Urad/ Black Till / Red Till/ Kulthi	-	-
	March-April	1 - Oct. -Nov. 2- March 3.-Oct. Nov.	-	-		-
Rabi	15 Oct. to 15 Nov.	Jan to Feb	Wheat	Mustard, Gram	Khesari	Relay cropping
	November	Feb		Masoor	-	Relay cropping
	November	Feb		- -		Relay cropping
Zaid	Feb-March	May-June		Vegetables		
	15 Jan -15 Feb	April			Black till	-
	15 Jan -15 Feb	April			-	-
	Feb-March	May-June				-

7.3 Traditional knowledge about seed biodiversity and seed system in the villages :

The region was full with pulses and oilseed biodiversity. The pulses and oilseed biodiversity was recorded in this region includes local varieties of Mustard, Black Gram, Black Till, Arhar, Moong, Kulthi, Khesari.

7.3.1 Pulses and oilseed biodiversity in the villages: Reason behind the changes in crops grown pattern in last 20-25 years

From this table, it can be observed that too many varieties of crops were grown at past in different seasons. But due to the reasons as mentioned in the table such as lack of labours, lack of storage, traditional plowing system and lack of farm mechanisation the number of varieties of seeds have been reduced.

Table - 4; % of Crop Grown and Pulses/Oilseed Biodiversity in the study area

Sl. No.	Villages name	Surveyed	% Grown Kharif Crop and name of crop	Sowing time for kharif	% Grown Rabi Crop and name of crop	Sowing time for Rabi	Rice Fallow area	Pulses and Oilseed : 20-25 years back	Reason behind for changes	Farmer interested to grown Pulses and Oilseed
1	Chihara	10	100 % and Rice	June-July	30% and Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	70%	Mustard, Raincha, Urad, Gram, Madua	Seed not available Labour not found Traditional plowing system -bull not available and mechanisation no there Rates are so low, which destroyed interest of farmer Seed provided by KVK or viagov. Supply was very poor quality. Protection require from animals	Black gram, Mustard, Channa, Masoor, Arhar, Khesari
2	Ghatiyani	10	100 % and Rice and Potato	June-july	35 % and Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	65%	Mustard, Raincha, Urad, Gram		Mustard, Black gram, Channa
3	Baredih	10	100 % Rice	June-july	32 % Rice Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	68%	Mustard, Raincha, Urad, Gram		Urad/Black gram, Mustard
4	Badladih	10	100% and Rice	June-july	35% Rice Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	65%	Mustard, Raincha, Urad, Gram		Black Gram/ Urad, Mustard,
5	Parsatan d	10	100 % Rice	June-july	25 % Rice Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	75%	Black Gram/ Urad and White Till in upper land and Black Till in Faagun month / feb, Moong, Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari in upper land		Black Gram/ Urad and White Till , Black Till, Moong, Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari
6	Sissia	10	100 % Rice	June-july	25 % Rice Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	75%	Black Gram/ Urad and White Till in upper land and Black Till in Faagun month / feb, Moong, Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari in upper land		Black Gram/ Urad and White Till , Black Till, Moong, Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari
7	Basahra	10	100 % Rice	June-july	28 % Rice Wheat, Till, Mustard	Nov.	72%	Black Gram/ Urad and White Till in upper land and Black Till in Faagun month / feb, Moong,		Black Gram/ Urad and White Till , Black Till, Moong,

								Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari in upper land		Arhar, Kulthi and Khesari
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7.3.2 Pulses and Oilseed : Seed Varieties, Pros. And Cons. of varieties , Uses and Faith about varieties

The table 5 Describes the varieties found at present in the project areas. As we can see, Farmers have only one seed of Kulthi, which they called “desi/local” varieties. They described that the local varieties grow well.

Table : 5; Seed Varieties, Pros. And Cons. of varieties , Uses and Faith about varieties

Villages	Pulses/Oil Seed	Name of crop	Varieties	Pros	Cons	Faith/Uses
Cehara	Pulses	Mustard, Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well	-	Kulthi used for kidney stone
Ghatiyani	Pulses	Mustard, Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well	-	
Baredih	Pulses	Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well	-	
Badladih	Pulses	Mustard (Sharsa) + Pigeon pea + Lentil (Masoor) +Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well	-	Kulthi used for kidney stone
Parsarand	Pulses	Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well	-	
Sirsiya	Pulses	Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well		
Bashara	Pulses	Green gram (Moong) + Lentil (Masoor), Kulthi	Desi/Local	Grown well		

Pulses Seed biodiversity: Bihar team collected the 15 farmers’ seeds during survey. These seeds were introduced in June / Monsoon Season 2020 through designing the Varietal Trial Farms for June -July season.

Total Farmer’s Varieties introduced in July Varietal Trial Plots, Bihar = 15 (Crops-4)

Crop Name	Arhar	Urad/ Black gram	Moong	Kulthi
	Pulses	Pulses	Pulses	Pulses
Farmer’s Varieties	1	5	2	7

The following motivated farmers contributed pulses seeds to local Seed Bank for scaling out of pulse cultivation.

SI	Name of the farmers	Habitation	Name of the seed / variety
1	SunitaBesra	Chihara	Mustard (Sharsa- desi)
2	NunwaHembrom	Ghatiyani	Green gram (Arhar dal- desi)
3	HareramYadavji	Beshara	Mustard (Sharson –desi)
4	JiwaSoren	Bashara	Lentil, Mustard (Mosur dal-desi)
5	Lakhanlal Hembrom	Badladih	Mustard (desi), maize

Bihar team were collecting the seed for August month’s Varietal Trial farm. This above list represents the seeds collected from the farmers. Collected seeds introduced as per trial plot design to screen the actual number of local varieties in the project area and to screen the appropriate variety.

7.3.3 Seed System :

A local seed supply system is a major dynamic factor that plays a crucial role in promoting crop evolution. It influences the structure and distribution of the on- farm crop genetic diversity at different scales. It has, therefore, a potential for dynamic maintenance of genetic diversity. Seed production and supply systems vary due to diversity of climate, crops, farming systems, cultures and economics. Commonly two types of seed systems or sectors are distinguished: ‘formal ’and ‘informal’.

“Village Haat” was major place to exchange the seed as it was the part of local market. About 20-25 years ago, seed systems were less diverse and most of the smallholder farmers got seeds from local, formal channels:

Fig. 20 - 25 years ago seed systems

Now, the present situation is fully changed. As Table -5, it was came into the survey that 86 % farmers purchased seeds from the market, 13 % people are dependent on government agencies and “Village Haat” was completely destroyed in the project areas. Today If we ask any farmer from a village -from where did you get the seed for farming, he would simply answer-“ from the shop”.

Table -6 : Formal and Informal Seed System

Purchase from Market	Dependent on KVK and governmental agency	Village Haat	General Seed -Exchange	Seed Exchange in Festival / Religious work
75%	0%	20%	5%	If there is shortage after purchasing from market

				or accessing from govt.
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7.3.4 Seed Storage:

Quality seed is the key input for realizing potential productivity. The main criteria for describing seed quality are purity, germination percentage and vigour of seeds. In most of the crops, the small and marginal farmers depend on their own farm saved seeds for crop production. Moreover, the crops are raised for market and a small portion of the grains are separated, stored and used as seeds in the next season which may not meet the quality aspects as expected for a seed which results in poor field stand and ultimately low yield.

“Mitti Ki Kothiya” was the earliest traditional seed storage system. Women usually made it by bamboo baskets wrapping with clay and cow dung. This traditional structure provided the isolation system to seed and prevents the air exchange with outer environment. Today, this kind of structure could not be found in these areas. Though we have found a structure of bamboo basket, covered by rice husk but not wrapping by clay and dung known as “Puaal”.

Seed Conservation Structure found in Jharkhand: This structure found in only one home during survey.

Munirka Devi, Bahronki, Jharkhand

Uses for seed storage

Uses for curd

Fig.- “Mitti ki Kothiya” – A Traditional Seed Conservation Structure (Image taken by Mr. Vikas Arora during field survey in Feb 2020)

Table -7 : Seed Storage Structure

% of surveyed	Present: seed storage	20-25 year back: Seed System	Reason behind change
59%	plastic bags, Steel Drum	Puaal and Kothi, CaCo3 layer	Loss of interest
30%	Salfose tablet	Bamboo baskets wrapping with clay and cow dung	Intensive Labour and lack of skill
11%	plastic bag + salfose tablet		

7.3.5 Seed convert into grain

Table -8 is showing the strong relation between traditional seed storage and grain storage, Table -8 is showing the present scenario of seed. 77% seeds were already consumed and only 4 % seeds were saved for next cycle. Seed storage structure played a important role to conserve biodiversity.

Table – 8: % of Seed, consumed as grain by surveyed

% of seed	Present: seed storage
55%	Consumed
15%	Saved for next crop cycle
30%	Destroyed by insect and damaged due to lack of scientific storage

7.4 Vulnerability to crops

7.4.1 Farmers' perception on climate change and adaptive response

Observed Changes in Weather Patterns:

We find that almost every surveyed farmer has noticed that weather patterns are changing. We collected data by focused group discussion of 10 respondents in each village. Respondents observed changes in weather patterns, such as higher temperatures in summer season along with increased duration, decrease frequency of hailstone, rain are more patchy, reduced amount of rainfall (From annual 3600 mm to 3200 mm for last 20 years). These data indicate that the global phenomenon of climate change is having pronounced effects at the local level.

Table - 9 : Change in climate : Community observations on different parameters

Villages	Rain: No. Of Days	Rain: Intensity Pre. Now	Rain: Patchy / equal distribution	Hail stone	Thunder storm	Summer : Intensity	Summer : No. Of Days	Winter: Intensity	Winter : No. Of Days
Cehara	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Ghatiyani	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Baredih	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Badladih	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Parsatand	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Sirsia	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Bashara	▼	▼	Patchy	▼	▼	▲	▲	▼	▼
Indicator s used by group	Now more suitable	Now more suitable: No Much tree falling; No continues rain like 15 to 20 days.	Uneven rainfall resulted in more pest attacked.	Now more suitable; Hailstone equal to zero	Suitable	Now not suitable ; We feel more sweating	Not suitable	Suitable	Suitable

In above table previous (pre.) represents the situation in 20-25 years ago.

▲ - The direction of arrow show the increase and colour show the climate not suitable for farmers at that point of time

▼ - The direction of arrow show the less and colour show the climate suitable for the point of time

7.4.2. Animals and other vulnerable factors

Due to non-availability of preferred dietary items in the original habitat, the animals are compelled to depend on agricultural crops for food and make enormous damage to the crops. They Damage to agricultural crops.

Table - 10: Vulnerable factor: Animals

Sl. No.	Villages name	No. of Surveyed	Animals name	Vulnerable for crops	Solution from community	Explain by community
1	Chihara	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Goat	Rice	Identifying the cow owners and warning them.	
2	Ghatiyani	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Goat,	Rice	Live Fencing	
3	Baredih	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Goat,	Rice	Group Farming	
4	Badladih	10	Bansuwar, Cow, birds etc.	Rice		
5	Parsatand	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Peacock, Parrot,	Rice, bamboo, Makai		
6	Sirsia	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Peacock, Parrot,	Rice, bamboo, Makai		
7	Basahra	10	Bansuwar, Cow, Peacock, Parrot,	Rice, bamboo, Makai		

CONCLUSION

Following are the major findings of the survey conducted in 7 villages where the BSF-IV cycle project for India is being implemented:-

1. Traditional knowledge for Pulses and Oilseed biodiversity is extremely destroyed in last 20-25 years.
2. 1 % of farmer grows pulses.
3. 80 % farmers want to grow pulses and oilseed crops but good quality of seeds are not available
4. The traditional seed storage and seed distribution system completely destroyed. "Village-Haat" does not work for exchanging or selling theseeds.
5. Animals are the most vulnerable factor in the study areas.
6. Women do not participate in any training or agriculture extension programme though major activities in agriculture are done by them only.
7. Major food in daily lifestyle is based on rice and vegetable (potato), pulses are absent or very low in quantity.
8. Large areas come under rice fallow.

RECOMMENDATION

1. To increase the pulses and oilseed biodiversity in monsoon season and post monsoon season.
2. Community Seed Bank should be functional for seed storage: collection, distribution of seed and preserve the biodiversity of pulses and oilseed of the region. This decentralized system where villagers themselves can plan, manage and undertake all stages of community seed bank.
3. To encourage farmers for reviving the knowledge of biodiversity of pulses and oilseed.
4. To increase the participation of women in training and extension services of agriculture.
5. To search adaptive and climate resilience varieties of pulses and oilseed, suitable for climate change.
6. Domestic animals like cow, goat can be controlled via live fencing / guard crop during Rabi season and kharif season i.e. four rows of Safflower or Castor as barrier crop.

Annexure-I

SELECTED VILLAGES AND FARMERS LIST WITH GPS LOCATION

Project under

Improving Pulse Biodiversity in Rice Fallow Areas of Tribal belts of Central and East Indian States to bring Resilience in the Farming Practices, Provide Livelihood Support and enhance Nutritional Level of the Tribal Population.

Visited Date: 1st to 9th January 2020
Survey by: Vikas Arora (Project Coordinator)
State Coordinator: Shri Upender Kumar
Supported By: Shri Subhash Dubey

1. 60 Farmers will be directly benefited from the Bihar state in the project site. The farmers list is attached.

Farmers Name and Villages will be directly Beneficial from this project:

STATE WISE – GENDER DISAGGREGATED LIST OF FARMERS

STATE BIHAR, DISTRICT-JAMUI, BLOCK-CHAKAI

TOTAL VILLAGE – 6

TOTAL FARMERS – 60

M-32, F-28

S.No	PANCHAYAT		VILLAGE NAME		NAME OF FARMER	M/F	FATHER/HUSBAND	MOBILE NO
1	DADHWA	1	BAREDIH	1	BADKI HEMBROM	M	NUNURAM HEMBROM	
2				2	JIVA SOREN	M	LT.SURBU SOREN	8294954181
3				3	FOLO HEMBROM	M	CHARO HEMBROM	9006865272
4				4	DILIP MURMU	M	LT. PURAN MARANDI	8262645835
5				5	JUNA MARANDI	F	LT. BARKU MARANDI	9693601269
6				6	GOVIND MARANDI	M	LT. BADKU MARANDI	8080625302
7				7	BINJU TUDU	M	ATWARI MARANDI	9360074034
8				8	SUNITA TUDU	F	SHANKAR MARANDI	7462026532
9				9	POOJA TUDU	F	RAMLAL SOREN	7461050878
10				10	BADAN MARANDI	M	JHARI MARANDI	7461050878
TOTAL – F=3 & M=7								
11		2	CHIHARA	1	SUNITA BESRA	F	SHIVLAL SOREN	7739576296
12				2	BABLU KUMAR SOREN	M	GOPAL SOREN	8210020473
13				3	VANDANA SOREN	F	LT. NANKU SOREN	
14				4	PARVATI SOREN	F	RAK KUMAR MARANDI	
15				5	TALO MURMU	F	VUDHAN SOREN	
16				6	BAHAMUNI MARANDI	F	RASILAL SOREN	7258966771
17				7	ANIL MURMU	M	LT. RASIK MURMU	
18				8	VIRENDER SOREN	M	LT. KISUN SOREN	
19				9	KARU SOREN	M	LT. KISUN SOREN	
20				10	SANICHAR KISKU	M	LT. LATHO KISKU	
TOTAL – F=5& M=5								
21		3	BADLADIH	1	KERMELI KISKU	F	PURAN TUDU	7782865869
22				2	LAKHAN LAL HMBROM	M	LT. HARIRAM HEMBROM	8051026810
23				3	SUKHDEV HEMBROM	M	BUDHU HEMBROM	
24				4	RAM KISHOR TUDU	M	LT. SAMAR TUDU	
25				5	MANOJ HEMBROM	M	LAKHAN LAL HEMBROM	8521391121
26				6	SUNNY SOREN	F	CHURKA HEMBROM	
27				7	JHUMARI MURMU	F	SONALAL TUDU	9065324433
28				8	MINA DEVI	F	NISOJ TUDU	
29				9	SUNITA SOREN	F	SIKANDER CHOUDE	7488088962
30				10	CHUTKA HMBROM	M	LT. MANJU HEMBROM	
TOTAL – F=5& M=5								
31		4	BASHARA	1	HARERAM YADAV	M	SOHAN YADAV	9199845106
32				2	RAJENDRA YADAV	M	JAGGANNATH YADAV	9546003208
33				3	JEERA CDEVI	F	PRADEEP YADAV	9161878159
34				4	DULARI DEVI	F	YOGENDRA YADAV	8292077282
35				5	SUNITA DEVI	F	RAJENDRA YADAV	9163543211
36				6	SUNITA DEVI	F	YOGENDRA YADAV	7765985184
37				7	SULIYA DEVI	F	SANTU YADAV	9006575383
38				8	TEKNARAYAN YADAV	M	ETWARI YADAV	7295967428
39				9	CHANDRASHEKHAR YADAV	M	YUGAL YADAV	8420841387
40				10	SUKHDEV YADAV	M	TEKNARAYAN YADAV	9939514396
TOTAL – F=5& M=5								
41	GHUTBWE	5	PARSATAR	1	REKHA KISKU	F	SANJAY HEMBROM	
42				2	PHOOLMUNI SOREN	F	CHOVA HEMBROM	
43				3	TALU KISKU	F	RAJESH MURMU	
44				4	REENA BASKI	F	MANOJ HEMBROM	
45				5	KUSANI HASDA	F	RAJIV HEMBROM	
TOTAL – F=5& M=0								
46		6	SIRSIA	6	MANGU HEMBROM	M	LT. SANGRAM HEMBROM	7739462059
47				7	TUKA BESRA	M	LT. NANKU BESRA	9835317119
48				8	JHUPLU HEMBROM	M	LT. GOPIN HEMBROM	
49				9	MUNSI HEMBROM	M	LT. PATKU MANJHI	
50				10	BHAIRO MURMU	M	LT. MAHALDA HEMBROM	
TOTAL – F=0& M=5								
51	NAWADIH SILPHARI	7	GHATIYANI	1	MOTILAL HEMBROM	M	LT. SHANKAR HEMBROM	6203961971
52				2	MANOJ HEMBROM	M	SARJU TUDU	
53				3	NUNWA HEMBROM	M	LT. HUKA HEMBROM	8292762640
54				4	MAHESH HEMBROM	M	SITAVI HEMBROM	6203344458
55				5	SUNITA SOREN	F	SANTOSH HANSDA	8521919419
56				6	TALO SOREN	F	ASHOK SOREN	7634919375
57				7	SAVITA MURMU	F	MUNNA HEMBROM	

58			8	RANDHO KISKU	F	MOTILAL HEMBROM	8459674994
59			9	RUPANI HEMBROM	F	BABULAL TUDU	
60			10	MAHENDRA TUDU	M	FAGU TUDU	9006530300
TOTAL – F=5& M=5							
